

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF STRESS AND HAPPINESS AMONG DRUG ADDICTED AND DRUG NON-ADDICTED ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

Drug addiction is a challenging, risky, and harmful habit that affects both mental and physical health. Drugs contain specific chemicals that alter brain function, potentially leading to unusual behaviors such as anxiety stress and depression etc. The present study was undertaken keeping these conditions in mind. Hence, the happiness and stress and their relations in drug addicted and drug-non-addicted adults were systematically measured and compared. Additionally the relationships of happiness and stress each other in both drug addicted and drug-non-addicted adults separately and combining were also studied. For this, purpose 60 drug addicted and 60 non-addicted adults of Bareilly U.P were availability selected and they were administered Young's Oxford happiness questionnaire and Perceived Stress Scale. The t-test was applied to analyze the data. The results as follows: The results indicated a significant difference in happiness and stress scores between drug-addicted and non-addicted individuals. Significant negative relationship between happiness and stress of drug addicted and drug-non-addicted adults were obtained. The review concludes with a summary of major research findings, as well as a consideration of future directions and implications for practice and policy.

Key words: Stress, Happiness, Drug-addicted and Non-addicted adults etc.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY:

Drug addiction is a big concern in today's environment. Many social and psychological factors contribute to addiction. A drug addict depends on the complicated drug-individual-society link, which indicates that society is playing a very vital part in becoming a drug addict (Jiloha RC, 2010). DSM-5-TR has offered a description of "frequent use and increased dependence on a substance that causes symptoms of discomfort and deprivation that has an uncontrollable desire to reuse the material" (Sadock BJ & Sadock VA, 2007). Khorramabadi (2014) claims that a variety of mental states, such as stress, depression, unpleasant states, or the removal of pain, cause drug addiction. The use of drugs can reduce these mental states, but only for the short term (Khorramabadi Y, 2014). As we said earlier, depression and stress are very common psychological disorders among drug addicts. Drug addicts fit the criteria for major depressive disorder, according to Sadock. The symptoms of depression can range from a week to months or years and include sadness, anxiety, helplessness, hopelessness, and more. A depressed person often has feelings of guilt and worthlessness, and these symptoms can cause drug abuse. Selye has defined stress as a condition when a person feels pressure to do something forcefully; it can be mentally, physically, or emotionally, and any cause that leads to pressure is called a stimulus. Stress is the main factor in the development of drug addiction. One definition of happiness is the state in which a person exhibits joy and contentment. It is the condition in which negative stress degrees are small, even if not zero, and positive stress improves the person's positive emotions. The present study was designed to assess the level of stress and happiness among drug-addicted and drug-non-addicted adults.

INTRODUCTION:

Drug addiction:

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines drug abuse as the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs (WHO, 2014). The National Institute of Drug Abuse (NIDA) defined drug abuse as a chronic, relapsing disorder characterized by compulsive drug seeking and use despite adverse consequences (NIDA, 2007). Drug abuse is the use of drugs for purposes or situations for which they are inappropriate, or even when they are appropriate but taken in excess of the recommended dosage. One of the most avoidable problems of our day is drug usage. It assumes the dimensions of a major worldwide catastrophe that affects people everywhere. But not everyone is aware of the effects of drug misuse; some people are more susceptible to it than others. The World Health Organisation estimates that drug addiction contributes significantly to the global burden of disease and disability, affecting between 3.4% and 6.6% of the population globally (World Drug Report, 2017). The World Drug Report (2017) estimates that drug misuse accounts for 0.4% of all fatalities each year, with amphetamine, cocaine, cannabis, and opioids being the most commonly used illicit substances globally.

Drug addiction, often referred to as drug use disorder, is a degenerative illness that makes a person lose control over their substance use even when the effects of their usage get worse. Substance abuse disorders can be fatal. Addictions are not issues of morality or willpower. The sickness of addiction is strong and intricate. Drug addicts are unable to stop using drugs, even if they so choose. Because of the way the medications alter the brain, it is tough to stop using them both psychologically and physically. Addiction is a disorder that alters behaviour and brain function. Drug addiction makes it impossible to resist the impulse to consume drugs, regardless of the potential risks. Your chances of avoiding some of the more severe effects of drug addiction increase with the timing of your therapy. Addiction treatment frequently calls for ongoing counselling and care.

Happiness:

Happiness may be found in a variety of settings. Stress and despair are common in today's nervous world. Therefore, it's critical that someone feels happy after leaving it. Any person's mental health will be maintained with its assistance. When someone is content, they continue to think positively about other individuals and all people. Additionally, he hopes that everyone is happy. A person with strong decision-making skills is also enthusiastic in his work and wants to help others. Happiness manifests itself in many ways for each individual. Some people find happiness in building a career, while others discover it in the joy of traveling. Some find joy in eating and drinking, while others value the bonds of social relationships. Many people find fulfillment in maintaining these connections and helping others, advocating for change against social injustices. Others seek happiness through their spiritual lives, following guidelines and principles while not being jealous of others. They strive to be compassionate towards everyone and uphold honesty in their interactions. Happiness is often experienced when someone has feelings for a person, an object, or an idea and then attains that desire. Different individuals find joy in various aspects of life, which positively impacts their experiences. Happiness is a vital component of existence, and fulfilling one's needs is essential for achieving it.

Definition of Happiness :

1. Happiness can be defined as an enduring state of mind consisting of not only feelings of joy, contentment, and other positive emotions, but of a sense, that one's life is meaningful and valued (Lyubomirsky, 2001).
2. Happiness, Aristotle suggested, could be achieved through the golden mean, which involves finding a balance between deficiency and excess. (Finley et al., 2020).
3. Happiness is an emotional state characterized by feelings of joy, satisfaction, contentment, and fulfillment. While happiness has many different definitions, it is often described as involving positive emotions and life satisfaction. (Kendra Cherry, 2022)

Happiness and Drug Addicts:

As a result, many people get hooked to various types of narcotics. In certain circumstances, it is even customary that if there is a happy mood on the occasion of marriage, they make it even joyful by abusing substances such as alcohol and marijuana. The issue goes all over the place, and it is clear that individuals use drugs to make themselves happy. Many individuals have faced the challenges of addiction, but the long-term effects of substance use are often not fully understood. While people may initially seek pleasure from these substances, they can have a detrimental impact on both mental and physical health. When under the influence of drugs, the brain may not function in real time, leading to significant damage over time. The repercussions extend beyond the individual, affecting the economy, society, and family dynamics. To live a happy life, it is essential to break free from addiction. Many addicts may feel that they can only find joy through substance use, but the reality is that true happiness exists outside of addiction. Individuals need to strive to avoid becoming dependent on these substances.

Stress:

Stress is a common human emotion that everyone experiences. The human body is designed to feel and respond to stress. When a person encounters changes or difficulties, known as stressors, their body and mind react accordingly. Stress reactions aid in your body's adaptation to novel circumstances. Stress can help us stay motivated, vigilant, and prepared to face danger. A stress reaction can motivate your body to work harder and stay awake longer, especially when an important event is approaching. However, stress becomes problematic when it lingers without any break or relief. It's a natural response your body has to changes, resulting in physical, emotional, and mental reactions. Your breathing, heart rate, vision, and other bodily functions are controlled by the autonomic nervous system. The "fight-or-flight response" is the body's natural reaction to stress, helping you cope with challenging situations. However, if this stress response is activated for an extended period due to chronic stress, it can take a toll on the body.

An inability to postpone pleasure and a loss of impulse control are linked to high emotional stress. In the area of the brain linked to stress management and cognitive control, chronic stress reduces grey matter volume. Stress causes the prefrontal cortex's deliberative cognition-related area to shut down. The brain that is under stress becomes automatic and loses its capacity for reflection. Stressed individuals are more likely to succumb to cravings such as smoking, binge eating, drinking, and abusing prescription drugs to manage their everyday stress (Grant et al., 2011).

Stress arises when individuals perceive that they cannot adequately cope with the demands being made on them or with threats to their well-being. R.S. Lazarus (1966).

Stress is the psychological, physiological and behavioural response by an individual when they perceive a lack of equilibrium between the demands placed upon them and their ability to meet those demands, which, over a period of time, leads to ill-health. S. Palmer (1989).

Stress can be defined as a state of worry or mental tension caused by a difficult situation. Stress is a natural human response that prompts us to address challenges and threats in our lives. Everyone experiences stress to some degree. (WHO, 2023).

Stress As A Risk Factor For Drug Addiction:

According to Koolhaas et al. (2011), stress is a neurophysiological and behavioral reaction that enables organisms to react to external challenges that are viewed as dangerous. The HPA axis and the autonomic nervous system, which are top-down mechanisms that prepare an organism for fight-or-flight or freeze responses and aid in homeostasis restoration, have direct control over this process (Koolhaas et al., 2011).

According to epidemiological research, stress is a major risk factor for drug addiction development and a powerful indicator of intense cravings and relapse (Mantsch et al., 2016). Prior to drug seeking or relapsing, people with cocaine and opioid dependence both describe going through stressful life situations (Khantzian, 1985). At baseline or following pharmacological and psychological stressors, they show elevated levels of stress-related hormones, such as CRF and ACTH (Contoreggi et al., 2003). Stress exposure has been shown to increase the rewarding effects of drugs and the development of drug-seeking behaviours in preclinical models of addiction. According to this viewpoint, stress promotes the development of connections between medicines and contextual information (Mantsch et al., 2016).

After studying this literature, we found that there have been independent and comparative studies done to learn about life satisfaction and happiness directly or indirectly, mostly among the population of drug users and abusers. Moreover, not much work has been done to explore these variables collectively and among the sample individuals of Recovered drug addicts. The purpose of our research is to analyse the lives of drug addicts after they had recovered to learn about the components of subjective well-being i.e., life satisfaction and happiness level, inclusively yet individually.

Significant of the study:

After reviewing this literature, we discovered that independent and comparative research has been conducted to find out more about happiness and stress, either directly or indirectly, mostly among drug addicted and drug non-addicted. Furthermore, there is a dearth of research on these factors both as a whole and among the sample of recovered drug users. The purpose of the suggested study was to assess the stress and happiness levels of both drug addicts and non-addicts in Indian socioeconomic circumstances. A comparison of the stress and happiness levels of drug addicts and non-addicts would examine various strategies for addiction rehabilitation. This knowledge might assist prevent further societal decline related to drug addiction or improve social stability.

Objective of the study:

The following objectives were formulated for the present study:

- To find out the difference in happiness between drug-addicted and drug non- addicted adults.

- To study the difference between in stress between drug-addicted and drug non-addicted adults.
- To explore the relationship between the happiness and stress of drug-addicted and non-addicted adults.

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated to empirically validate the above objectives:

- There would be significant difference in happiness between drug-addicted and drug non-addicted adults.
- There would be significant difference in stress between drug-addicts and drug non-addicted adults.
- There would be a significant relationship between the happiness and stress of drug-addicted and non-addicted adults.

Sample

In the current study, over 60 drug users from Baraley, Uttar Pradesh, including those who use alcohol, tobacco, heroin, and other substances, were chosen. This study included both drug addicts (all male patients admitted to the drug de-addiction and rehabilitation clinic in the Bareilly, U.P.) and non-drug addicts (other men who were not using any sort of drug). Data was collected in Bareilly, U.P. Since males were more likely than women to use drugs, it was necessary to conduct the research exclusively on men, and the majority of the studies were conducted on adults. The rehabilitation center's authorities granted ethical clearance, and both the patients—drug addicts—and those who weren't drug addicts gave their informed permission. 60 patients between the ages of 19 and 40 were chosen for the sample using the purposive sampling approach, and 60 non-drug addicts in the same age range were chosen for the other groups.

Tools:

Psychotic patients were not included in the research because they were unable to react appropriately. A number of psychological instruments were used, starting with the Perceived Stress Scale. The perceived stress scale was created to gauge how stressful a person believes certain events in their life to be. This is a self-report rating inventory with ten items. In a university sample, reliability evaluations for reported helplessness and perceived self-efficacy scores were 0.85 and 0.82, respectively. and the third was the Oxford Happiness Questionnaire, which was created at Oxford University by psychologists Peter Hills and Michael Argyle. The 29-item scale has strong concept validity, internal consistency reliability ($\alpha = 0.92$), and a positive correlation with extraversion ($r = 0.38$ $p < 0.001$) and a negative correlation with neuroticism ($r = -0.57$ $p < 0.001$). The study's premise stated that drug users would have greater levels of stress and sadness but not happiness.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

A two groups design (drug-addicted and drug non-addicted) and correlational design were used in the present study. A two-group design is used when the researcher divides his or her subjects into two groups and then compares the results. In the present study, there were two groups, viz, drug-addicted and drug non-addicted adults.

Results and Discussion:

Hypothesis-1: There would be significant difference in happiness between drug-addicts and drug non--addicted adults.

Table no-1

Means, SDs, and results of t-ratio of Drug addicted and Drug Non- addicted adults on happiness

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	t	Sig. Level
Happiness	Drug addicted	60	80.77	30.1	118	3.60	< .01
	Non-drug addicted	60	108.37	29.3			

Table- 1 shows that mean happiness score of drug addicted and non- drug addicted adults were 80.77 and 108.37 respectively. The SDs of happiness score of drug addicted and non- drug adults were found 30.1 and 29.3 respectively. Their respective df was 118. The t- ratios between means happiness scores of the two groups were found as 3.60, which was significant at level of 0.01. It means that there is statistical difference on the scores of happiness score of drug addicted and non- drug addicted adults. The findings of the present study did confirm the hypothesis -1 which states that “there would be significant difference in happiness between drug-addicted and drug non--addicted adults” was proved true by the finding of the study. Since the t-ratio came to be significant it can be said that non-drug addicted adults are significantly more happiness than drug addicted adults.

Hypothesis-2: There would be significant difference in stress between drug-addicts and drug non--addicted adults.

Table no-2

Means, SDs, and results of t-ratio of drug-addicts and drug non--addicted adults on stress

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	t	Sig. Level
Stress	Drug addicted	60	25.27	7.35	118	2.70	< .01
	Non-drug addicted	60	20	5.95			

Table- 2 shows that mean stress score of drug addicted and non- drug addicted adults were 25.27 and 20 respectively. The SDs of stress score of drug addicted and non- drug adults were found 7.35 and 5.95 respectively. Their respective df was 118. The t- ratios between means happiness scores of the two groups were found as 2.70, which was significant at level of 0.01. It means that there is statistical difference on the scores of stress score of drug addicted and non- drug addicted adults. The findings of the present study did confirm the

hypothesis -1 which states that “there would be significant difference in stress between **drug-addicts and drug non--addicted adults**” was proved true by the finding of the study. Since the t-ratio came to be significant it can be said that drug addicted school students are significantly more stress than non drug addicted adults.

Table no. 3

Results of Correlation between happiness and stress of drug-addicted adults.

Variables	Correlation	Significance level
Happiness Stress	-0.652	<.01

Table no. 4

Results of Correlation between happiness and stress of drug non-addicted adults.

Variables	Correlation	Significance level
Happiness Stress	-0.504	<.01

If we look at Table 3, we will find that coefficient of correlation between happiness and stress scores of drug-addicted adults was found as $r = -0.652$, which was significant at the .01 level of significance. But, the value of the coefficient of correlation was negative, meaning thereby that the two variables are inversely related to each other. In Table 4, the coefficient of correlation $r = -0.504$ between the happiness and stress scores of drug-non-addicted adults was found to be negative and significant at the 0.01 level of significance. The table clearly shows that increasing the stress score also decreases the happiness score. So, the hypothesis-3 that says that “there would be a significant relationship between the happiness and stress of drug-addicted and non-addicted adults” was accepted.

DISCUSSION:

The present study aimed to determine if stress and happiness levels in opium addicts differ from those of normal subjects. Based on the first hypothesis of the study, findings showed that drug-non-addicted adults are significantly happier than drug-addicted adults. Long-term use of drugs of abuse causes structural alterations in essential brain regions that underpin memory, executive function, and cognitive processes. According to Ersche et al. (2013), chronic cocaine users appear to experience a "fast-track" ageing process in their brains, with the prefrontal and temporal cortices appearing to be most affected by this grey matter reduction. The current study's findings are comparable to those of Kelly (1999), who did similar research and discovered that drug usage was the primary factor related to decrease psychological well-being. According to Tuicomepee and Romano (2005), Thai drug users have poor levels of psychological well-being. Visser and Routledge (2007) discovered that adolescents who take drugs had considerably poorer levels of psychological well-being and life satisfaction. Farmer and Hanratty (2012) discovered that respondents in England who reported being happy or able to interact with their family were less likely to be regular users.

The discussion can be concluded by highlighting the following significant findings from this study: Drug addicts experience significantly lower overall happiness compared to non-addicts. This decline in happiness is a direct consequence of drug addiction, which can

ultimately impair an individual for the rest of their life. Furthermore, the alarming rise in drug addiction poses a serious threat to society. Authorities must take immediate action to eradicate this issue in order to protect dynamic and productive individuals from a tragic fate.

On the basis of second hypothesis of the study, findings showed that drug-addicted school students are significantly more stress than drug non-addicted adults. Our findings are consistent with earlier studies on the association between stress and drug use (Kiluk, Nich, & Carroll, 2011; Valentino, Lucki, & Van Bockstaele, 2010; Sinha, 2009; Wills & Hirky, 1996; Wagner, Myers, & McIninch, 1999). The research on stress and drug abuse has demonstrated a relationship (Arevalo, Prado, & Amaro, 2008; Goeders, 2003). According to some research, stress increases an individual's vulnerability to substance abuse, both biologically (for example, by chronic stress-mediated changes to the dopaminergic system) and psychologically, through impaired coping skills and increased sensitivity to negative affect (Constantinou et al., 2010). Stress may also impact on the salience of stimuli which are associated with an individual's habitual drug use. Conditioned responses to stimuli associated with drug use are known to play an important role in both the maintenance of addiction and precipitation of relapse (Constantinou et. al., 2010).

On the basis of third hypothesis of the study, findings showed that two variables are inversely related to each other. It was confirmed that the variables would have an inverse relationship. Participants who felt more stressed out expressed less happiness, whereas those who felt less stressed expressed more happiness. The detrimental effects of stress on well-being have been studied in connection to happiness. Some studies have shown that, stress has a negative impact on well-being (Chatters 1988; Suh et al. 1996; Zika and Chamberlain 1987), whereas other studies have not (Feist et al. 1995). The present study's findings support the idea that happiness and perceived stress are inversely related.

CONCLUSION:

The present study was conducted with the objectives to investigate the difference between drug addicted and drug non-addicted on stress and happiness adults. For this purpose 60 drug addicted and 45 drug non- addicted (total=120) adults were selected from different rehabilitation center of Bareilly U.P. They were administered the perceived stress Scale measuring stress and oxford happiness questionnaire for measuring happiness. t-test was used to find out the difference between drug addicted and drug non-addicted separately. The following results were obtained:

1. The results of t- test reveal that there was significant difference between drug addicted and drug non-addicted on happiness.
2. A significant difference between drug addicted and drug non-addicted on stress.
3. Happiness is negatively correlated with stress in both drug-addicted and non-drug-addicted adults

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